

Effect of storage time on insecticide-treated rice seeds

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Insecticide treatment of rice seed has several advantages and has application for direct-seeded rice (dryland or wetland) and transplanted rice in the seedbed. Insecticides considered for seed treatment should satisfy certain requirements before recommendation; the most important is that they must not adversely affect germination of seeds or the seedlings. Sometimes seed are not sown immediately after treatment, so we measured the effect of storage on germination in an experiment from July to September 1979 with eight insecticides—carbofuran, bendiocarb, phenthoate, chlorthiophos, methoxychlor, cartap, formetanate, and promecarb. A 25% gum arabic water solution (sticker) was added to IR36 seeds in a plastic bag and the seeds were hand-agitated until the surfaces were evenly coated. Insecticides were then added at 10 g a.i./ kg and were agitated again to ensure uniform coverage. The treated seeds were then dried in the shade and stored for 8-weeks in a non-airconditioned room (temp, 28-30°C; relative humidity, 80%). Germination percentage was taken at weekly intervals by placing 25 seeds in petri dishes on filter paper with moistened cotton wads. Each treatment was replicated four times and arranged in a completely randomized design.

All insecticides showed phytotoxicity up to 8 weeks after treatment (see table). Chlorthiophos, promecarb, and bendiocarb had immediate phytotoxic effects on seeds germinated on the same day that they were treated. But bendiocarb-treated seeds showed no phytotoxic effects from 1 to 5 weeks after treatment, indicating that the insecticide degraded over the 1st week to a less active ingredient. Cartap and formetanate were highly phytotoxic for 1 to 2 weeks respectively, after storage, indicating that degradation products were perhaps toxic.

Germination of insecticide-treated seeds of IR36 with time of storage. IRRI, 1979 a/									
Germination (%) at indicated weeks after treatment									
Insecticide	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
Check	100a	95 a	95 a	95 a	100a	80a	95 a	100a	100 a
Bendiocarb 80 WP	75 bc	85 ab	85 ab	95 a	95 ab	85 a	85 b	85 b	95 a
Promecarb (Carbamult 38)	75 bc	75 b	70 bc	55 cd	90 ab	55 c	65 c	70 c	85 b
Carbofuran (Furadan 2F)	90 abc	90 ab	90 a	75 abc	85 b	80 ab	75 bc	75 bc	75 bc
Phenthoate (Pennant 40 SP)	95 ab	85 ab	70 bc	65 c	80 b	75 ab	70 c	70 c	75 bc
Methoxychlor (Marlate 50 SP)	90 abc	90 ab	90 a	90 ab	85 b	75 ab	65 c	75 bc	75 bc
Chlorthiophos (Celathion 25 SP)	65 c	90 ab	95 a	70 bc	95 ab	65 bc	75 bc	80 bc	70 c
Cartap (Padan 50 SP)	90 ab	25 c	35 d	0 d	0 d	0 d	0 d	0 d	0 d
Formetanate (Dicarzol50)	95 bc	85 ab	65 c	30 d	25 c	0 d	0 d	0 d	0 d
a/ All insecticides were applied at 10 g a.i./kg seed, with 25% gum arabic water solution as sticker. Av of 4 replications, 25 seeds/replication.									
b/ In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.									
c / Day of treatment									

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